

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Némethy****FIRST NAME: Dániel****PROGRAM CODE: DRCTh****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author used Zotero to insert references
The author used Grammarly Premium
The author used the following software: MSWord M365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is the right order from generic to specific on research related notions?**
 - Research problem, research topic, research question.
 - Research question, research problem, research topic.
 - Research topic, research question, research problem.
 - Research topic, research problem, research question.**¹

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore: SAGE Publications, 2008), 36.

2. **Which words are capitalized in the headline style?**

- Capitalize the first letter of the first and last words and all major words.**²
- Capitalize all major words except the last one.
- Capitalize the title as a normal sentence.
- Capitalize all nouns in the title.

3. **What is the main purpose of the literature review?**

- Summarizes of the topic-relevant contents of articles and books.
- Analyzes and criticizes former research on the paper subject.
- Puts the paper in the context of another research and sets up the next step.**³
- Explains the background of the researcher and his or her motivation.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 103.

³ Turabian, 30; Bloomberg and Volpe, 46.

4. **Which author is behind the Greek transcription Τζορτζ Μπέρναρντ Σο?**

- Tzortz Mpernarnt So.
- Jorge Bernhardt.
- George Mpernar-Soul.
- George Bernard Shaw.**⁴

5. **What is *not* an aspect of style.**

- Paragraph numbering and indentation.
- Voice preferences (active or passive).
- Content of conclusion.**⁵
- Use of lists.

6. **What is the Oxford comma?**

- It is the comma appearing before the conjunction joining the last two elements in a series.**⁶
- It is the comma before the coordinating conjunction of two independent clauses.
- It is the first of the paired commas to set off a nonrestrictive clause.
- It is the second of the paired commas to set off a nonrestrictive clause.

⁴ Tim Cooper et al., eds., *English Style Guide*, 8th ed. (European Commission's Directorate-General for Translation, 2020), 83.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 24–25.

⁶ University of Chicago. Press and University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, *The Chicago Manual of Style*, Chicago Manual of Style (University of Chicago Press, 2017), sec. 6.19.

7. **What is *not* part of the study writing process?**

- Presenting methodology and research approach.
- Analyzing and criticizing former studies.**⁷
- Analyzing and interpreting findings.
- Presenting actionable recommendations.

8. **Which is a correct citation of the Bible?**

- 1 Sam 2,1-5.
- 1 Sam: 2.1-5 NAB.
- 1Sam NRSV 2:1-5.
- 1 Sam 2:1–5 NRSV.**⁸

9. **What is plagiarism?**

- When the writer does not quote precisely the author he or she is referring to.
- Paraphrasing a source but giving the place of the reference.
- When the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.**⁹
- Consequently, omitting the page number from the citation.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, vi.

⁸ Turabian, sec. 24.6.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 5.

10. Which research method is typical for quantitative research?

- Mixed.
- Critical Theory.
- Postpositivist.**¹⁰
- Pragmatic.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 13.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.